

THE NECESSITY OF USING THE AUDIO-RESOURCES AT THE ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract. *This article describes The audio-visual aids have an important role in improving the speaking skills of the students, because there are so many advantages we can take by using audio-visual aids. Practically the use of audio–visual aids is one of the appropriate techniques to improve students’ speaking skills.*

Keywords: *audio-lingual, podcasts, modern methods, techniques, approaches.*

The problem of the importance and expediency of the use of listening techniques resources in foreign language education has been increasingly raised in the area of foreign language teaching, which involves not only the analysis of the use of new technical means, but also the study of the positive and negative aspects of the introduction of innovative forms and methods of teaching. Modern methods of teaching foreign languages are associated with the ongoing technological progress, as well as with the technological update of the learning process. The audio-visual aids have an important role in improving the speaking skills of the students, because there are so many advantages we can take by using audio-visual aids. Practically the use of audio–visual aids is one of the appropriate techniques to improve students’ speaking skills. Through audio–visual aids, the students are more enthusiastic. Learners enjoyed the process of teaching and learning more. Teaching speaking using audio–visual aids gives a big chance to the students to speak. It also provides an opportunity to develop accuracy, fluency and keeps the learners highly motivated. The facilities already provided by the school, it is regrettable if the teacher did not use them. formation of critical thinking of modern students. The use of listening skills in teaching a foreign language is due not only to the desire to modernize the learning process, but also to the fact that on the basis of web technologies it becomes possible to implement a person-oriented approach to both the learner and the entire learning process in General, which is the main direction of education in our time.

The latest multimedia and Internet technologies help to quickly and effectively master the perception of listening skills, put the correct pronunciation, learn grammar rules, master fluent reading and a deep understanding of real texts, create real situations of communication, remove psychological barriers and increase interest in the language. All this is the most important task of learning a foreign language to improve the skills already acquired and the development of new ones. At the moment, the Internet provides exceptional opportunities for learning a foreign language, as it provides an opportunity for live communication in the target language, provides access to all kinds of authentic materials and a huge number of learning resources in text, audio and video formats. In the context of language education, this allows creating a technological learning language environment for the formation of foreign language competences of students. Internet resources provide teachers and learners with special foreign language training programs, country study material, economic and political news, culture, the necessary authentic literature, the selection of which the teacher can conduct independently and adapt to specific educational goals. Learners, in turn, with the right choice of material, programs, resources have the opportunity

to participate in online conferences, webinars, competitions, create multimedia presentations in the process of working on projects. Thus, learners are in constant contact with a foreign language both at school and in the preparation of homework via the Internet. Moreover, the use of Internet resources both in school activities and in self-study of learners makes it possible to develop all types of speech activity. For example, oral speech is developed through the use of video conferences using a webcam or appropriate web resources (Skype, Live Messenger).

Written language is improved with the use of social networks (Facebook, Twitter), where learners have the opportunity to practice written communication skills with classmates, as well as with the native speakers of the studied language. Thus, communication is not limited to the topics specified in the school, which makes it possible to create a real situation of interaction in a foreign language, where learners unconsciously work out grammatical structures and train their active vocabulary. Therefore, it can be concluded that distance learning contributes to the solution of one of the pressing problems of interpersonal and intercultural communication, when the student is removed from the teacher geographically.

There are several types of Internet services that can be used for independent work of students:

1. Hotlist (list on the topic) - is a kind of list of sites with texts on the topic under study. If the user wants to create it, he needs to enter a keyword in the search engine.

2. Multimedia scrapbook (multimedia draft) – appears as a system of multimedia resources, where in addition to links to text sites, there are also a large number of multimedia materials, including tables, photos, audio files and video clips, graphic information, animation virtual tours. These files can be easily downloaded by both teachers and students and can be used as a visual demonstration material when studying a specific topic.

3. Treasure hunt – is a web resource where in addition to links to various sites you can find questions on the content of each site. With the help of these questions the teacher can control the cognitive activity of students. At the end of the search can be asked one more General question on a comprehensive understanding of the topic. This request will receive a detailed response, which will include answers to more detailed questions on each of the sites.

4. Sample subject is a site that occupies the next level of complexity compared to the previous resource. It also contains links to text and multimedia materials on the Internet. As part of the work with this resource, the user should not just get acquainted with the material, but also to Express and argue their opinion on the issue under study.

5. WebQuest (Internet project)-is the most complex type of online learning resources. This resource includes the scenario of the organization of project activities on the topic chosen by the teacher using the Internet resources. Summarizing the information obtained during the study of these services, we can note that using the Internet in educational activities, the teacher needs to clearly understand the feasibility of its application at a certain stage of training, all the positive and negative aspects of the introduction of web technologies.

The use of web resources in school classes and in self-preparation of students, taking into account the age, psychological, individual characteristics of students of any age, will successfully assimilate language information and develop speech skills, make the educational process more interesting, bright, informative, affect all kinds of memory and all ways of perception of language material, thereby facilitating the process of learning a foreign language for both teachers and students. In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of Internet resources and multimedia gives

teachers an excellent opportunity to improve learning management, increase the efficiency and objectivity of the educational process, save time of the teacher, increase the motivation of students to acquire knowledge, interest them in learning foreign languages, instill a strong desire for self-control and self-improvement, which will have a positive impact on learning outcomes.

Moreover, using web resources, teachers greatly simplify the process of communication of students with each other and with native speakers, as students are able to communicate both in writing and orally through video conferences or social networks, not only on school topics, and discovering the situation of daily communication, as close to communication in real conditions.

The main purpose of foreign language teaching is the formation and the development of the communicative culture of schoolchildren learning the practical mastering a foreign language. The teacher's task is to create appropriate conditions for practical language acquisition, selection of training methods that would allow each learner to show their activity, their creativity. The task of the teacher-student learning increased in learning foreign languages. Modern teaching technologies such as collaboration, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources help you implement student-oriented approach in teaching, provide individualization and differentiation of the learning abilities of children, taking into account their level of teaching, dispositions, etc.

Forms of work with computer training programs in English lessons include:

- vocabulary;
- development of pronunciation;
- training of Dialogic and monologue speech;
- training letter;
- development of grammatical phenomena.

Ability to use Internet resources is enormous. The global network of the Internet creates new conditions for the students and teachers of any required information from anywhere in the world: regional geography's material news from the life of the young, articles from newspapers and magazines, literature, etc. There is a need to bring the teaching of English at the school in line with the development of modern information technology. English language lessons with the help of the Internet, you can solve a number of didactic objectives: build reading skills, using materials of the global network; improve the writing skills of students; enrich vocabulary students; create sustainable motivation for students learning English.

Learners can take part in the testing, quizzes, competitions, Olympiads, held by the Internet, communicate with peers from other countries, participate in chat rooms, video conferencing, etc., students can get information on the problem, on which work is currently in the project. This may be the joint work of Uzbek students and their foreign peers from one or more countries.

One of the most revolutionary advances over the past decade, which significantly influenced the educational process in the world, was the creation of the world computer network known as the Internet, which literally means "international network".

The use of cyberspace for training purposes is absolutely a new direction of General didactics and private methods, because the changes affect all aspects of the educational process, from choosing the methods and style of work, to the changing requirements of the academic level of students.

The substantial base of mass computerization of education, of course, is that modern computer is an effective tool for optimizing the terms of mental work at all, in any of its manifestations.

Communicating in the true language environment provided by the Internet, students find themselves in these situations. Involved in a wide range of meaningful, realistic and achievable targets of interest, students learn spontaneously and adequately respond to them, that stimulate the creation of original utterances, not template manipulation language formulas.

The focus is on understanding the transfer of content and expression of meaning that motivates the study of the structure and vocabulary of a foreign language, which serve this purpose. Thus, the students focused on the use of shapes, rather than themselves, and teaching grammar is indirect, direct communication, excluding pure study of grammatical rules.

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